

Samagra Shiksha under Vocational Education

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Abstract

One mechanism that may help get us closer to our aim of offering high-quality education to all students is the shift toward a more digitally-based curriculum. Every nation employs this method. The universal integrated program Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan now includes digital activities as a core component, as announced by the Government of India and the Ministry of Human Resource Development on May 24, 2018. The scheme's overall program for the educational sector was introduced to take a comprehensive and undivided approach to schooling from the earliest years (nursery school) through the later years (high school). An essential objective is the elimination of the gap between the sexes and socioeconomic groups in all educational settings. The Vocationalization of School Education initiative is being carried out through the Centrally Sponsored Programme Samagra Shiksha - an integrated system for school education. All in-service training programs might be consolidated under one plan by the State Council of Educational Research and Training, making them more responsive to changing needs. If the states of the Society were to take use of the program's technological benefits, more individuals in the society could be able to access and benefit from a high-quality education.

Key words: Inclusive education, Integrated, Dynamic and Vocationalization

Introduction

The Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan is an all-encompassing initiative that provides financial aid to the states of India with the goal of improving the quality of elementary and secondary education throughout the country. Social justice content should include discussions on how to best foster the development and well-being of human capital. This article details the history of the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan, the initiatives it aims to implement, and the various government projects it has merged with. As an added bonus, it emphasizes several salient features of the software. Preparers for the IAS Exam will get a lot of knowledge and insight into the exam's content from this section. A decentralized planning activity is currently being carried out with the involvement of all key stakeholders to ensure that the plan is effective in achieving the overall purpose. Now, every state is hard at work on an exhaustive action plan that will cover every Samagra Shiksha initiative from now through the conclusion of the current fiscal year (2025-2026). This action is being taken so that the planned outcomes of the programs may be realized.

Vocational Education

There is a focus on practical training and skill improvement in the NEP 2020. Key changes in the education system have been recognized, and they center on the mainstreaming and integration of vocational education with general education. Samagra Shiksha, an existing vocational education program, has been updated and expanded to meet the goals of the National Education Program these are examples of a few:

- Vocational education now includes both publicly funded and publicly subsidized institutions.
- The Hub and Spoke Model of Vocational Education allows students from adjacent schools to take use of the facilities of Hub schools while pursuing their trade education.
- Upper Primary students will be exposed to a variety of pre-vocational courses.

- The Innovation part of Samagra Shiksha now includes things like internships and bagless days.
- A fun course for class VI to VIII students provides hands-on experience in a variety of vocational crafts, such as carpentry, electric work, metal work, gardening, pottery making, and more.
- Class VI-8 students may intern with local carpenters, gardeners, potters, painters, etc.

The program has a provision for giving students in Classes VI through VIII exposure to vocational education with the goal of giving students the chance to become familiar with the skills required for the various occupations in a sector and empowering them to make educated decisions when choosing their subjects. The following occupations are now offered via vocational training programs:

- Healthcare
- Beauty & Wellness
- Retail
- Travel & Tourism
- Automotive
- Agriculture
- Apparel Made-Ups Home Furnishing
- Electronics and Hardware

In addition to government schools, support was provided under the vocational education program at government-aided schools as well. The amount of funding, as well as the number of employment positions and sections, was proportional to the number of students enrolled in the program. The provision of classroom and workshop space for vocational education at schools that serve as hubs for other schools in the surrounding area. Students are able to obtain first-hand experience in the field of their choice before even graduating from their academic programs if they choose vocational education and training. Students who successfully complete these demanding programs are equipped with the qualifications and practical experience necessary to launch their chosen careers as soon as they graduate.

Modifications in the Revised Scheme of Vocational Education

Vocational education starting in Class IX. 75:25 Centre-state split for total plan money. North Eastern states, including Sikkim, get 90:10 funding. A flexible pool of Rs. 14.50 lakhs per school for resource individuals like instructors, skill knowledge providers, trainers, etc. Funding for Industry/Sector Skill Councils evaluation, certification, and training. Funding for books and e-learning. Innovative vocational education programs get 1% of funding. Curriculum and learning materials cost up to Rs. 2.00 lakhs per skill level per job type.

Objectives of the scheme of Vocational Education

Vocationalization of secondary and higher secondary education is a program that is sponsored by the central government with the goals of (i) increasing the employability of youth through demand-driven competency-based modular vocational courses, (ii) preserving their competitiveness through the provision of multi-entry multi-exit learning opportunities and vertical mobility/interchangeability in qualifications, (iii) closing the gap between the educated and the employable, and (iv) lowering the unemployment rate. These are the specific goals.

Objectives of Samagra Shiksha

This initiative was launched by the Human Resource Development Bureau of the Indian government. The Department of Literacy and Elementary Education is in charge of it.

- To improve education as a whole is the program's primary objective.
- Grasp the value of education for what it is. Without the chance to put what they have learned into practice, a child's education is useless. Maintaining the plan's instructional integrity is a top priority. Vocational training as an alternative to or supplement to college-level study is being considered.

- The Plan is a radical break from conventional methods of educational planning since it treats "school" as an umbrella term that includes pre-school, primary school, middle school, and high school.
- Gender inequality is a major issue in the nation. The rollout of the new initiative will help the government in its quest for educational parity. Because of this, educational opportunities for children of both sexes will be equalized.
- The plan's primary motivation was to raise standards across the board in terms of both student access and learning outcomes.
- States get funding under the Samagra Shiksha plan to improve their educational facilities, particularly those in rural regions.

Origins of the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan

The Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan unites these three initiatives in an effort to provide all pupils a complete education.

- Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan,
- Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan
- Teacher Education

The goal is to provide a smooth transition between primary and secondary education. Its goal is to improve education worldwide by fostering collaboration between teachers and technology-based resources. The Ministry of Human Resource Development is implementing the Programme of Vocationalisation of School Education under the auspices of Samagra Shiksha. High school students have the potential to get the skills and education necessary for employment in a broad variety of fields. The goal of creating an educational system that does not compartmentalize pupils but rather encourages them to work together toward a common goal is essential in the quest for a meaningful and useful education. The program's overarching objective is to provide young people with the ecological literacy and self-sufficiency necessary to reach their full intellectual, emotional, and physical potential. This attempt ought to be a process of value-based education that gives young people an opportunity to work toward the greater good rather than just their own.

Excellent Financial aid for Schooling

The approach of budgeting has been expanded. The allocation of resources for the program will be based on the approach that will be utilized to create outcomes and the activities that will be done to enhance the quality. Committed to improving education for the benefit of students by emphasizing two factors—technology and the time and care of instructors—to achieve positive outcomes. Increases pupils' potential for learning and is applicable to both analog and digital forms of education. Efforts to raise student achievement center on expanding programs like DIETs, BRCs, CRCs, CTEs, and IASEs, which prepare future educators in the classroom. Almost a million schools and colleges have access to library endowments. Aims to fairly share resources with those who actively seek expert outcomes.

Samagra Shiksha Scheme's Vision

1. The program's major objective is to provide assistance to states so that they may fulfill the requirements of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act of 2009. The right to an education is enshrined in Article 21-A of the Indian Constitution. Further details about the Right to Education Act may be found at the linked page.
2. The second Sustainable Development Goal is to ensure that all children, regardless of their families' socioeconomic condition, have access to a good quality education from pre-school through high school.

Samagra Shiksha Highlights

The project ensures all pupils a decent education by increasing the number of schools in disadvantaged regions and boosting their highest level of education to secondary. It ensures schools satisfy government criteria with enough amenities. Digital boards, smart classrooms, and direct-to-home television channels from Samagra Shiksha help schools employ digital technologies. Federal money

helps states and territories meet Right to Education Act requirements. This initiative funds start-up residential schools and hostels for troubled youths. The approach suggests starting with "special attention districts," "educationally backward blocks," and "left-wing extremism impacted areas." Samagra Shiksha funds teacher in-service training, composite grants to every school to establish a learning environment, grants for the library, sports, and physical activities, assistance for IT and digital projects, and the Rashtriya Avishkar Abhiyan.

Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan Improves Girls' School Enrollment

According to the Ministry of Education, the number of Indian girls attending school thanks to the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan rose between 2018 and 2020. The Ministry released a press statement on the sector's important achievements on Wednesday. The Gross Enrollment Ratio, a measure of students' engagement in formal education, has increased annually in 2018, 2019, and 2020. (Duraismy, 2006). According to the Unified District Information System for Education (UDISE) and UDISE +, the Gross Enrollment Ratio of female students has grown from 101.78 in 2018-19 to 103.69 in 2019-20, and from 88.54 in 2018-19 to 91.46 in 2019-20 at the upper elementary level. A press release from the Ministry of Education indicated that the Secondary sector's Gross Enrollment Ratio increased from 76.93 in 2018-19 to 77.83 in 2019-20, while the Higher Secondary sector's GER increased from 50.84 to 52.40. Samagra Shiksha aims to promote equality and student engagement throughout the educational process, as stated by the country's Ministry of Education. Samagra Shiksha has established Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalayas (KGBVs) in Educationally Backward Blocks for girls from marginalized communities (such as SC, ST, OBC, minority, and BPL) (BPL). Students in grades 6-8 in the earlier Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan were allowed to use KGBVs. Samagra Shiksha provides money to improve and expand existing KGBVs, as well as to combine such buildings with girls' dormitories up to the eleventh and twelfth grades, in an effort to reduce dropout rates and boost female participation in secondary and higher education. In KGBVs, girls get a specialized, practical education catered to their unique interests and goals.

Padhe Bharat Badhe Bharat

Padhe Bharat Badhe Bharat, a countrywide subprogramme of the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (Pandey, 2014). If kids don't learn to read early on, they fall behind in other subjects. The curriculum will improve early reading, writing, and math for Classes I and II. The software will achieve this. This scheme gave each state 762 billion rupees. The initiative will provide a print-rich atmosphere, timely book distribution, and a new teacher mentorship and evaluation system. Together with book distribution. The reforms' new primary education strategy and vision will be based on these principles: The National Curriculum Framework requires a thorough rethinking of curriculum, teacher training, educational planning, and administration. Equality is not just equal chance but also creating conditions for disadvantaged children, such as SC, ST, Muslim minority, landless agricultural workers, and children with special needs, to participate. Special-needs kids are included. Access means understanding the educational needs and predicament of traditionally excluded groups, such as the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and other sections of the most disadvantaged groups, the Muslim minority, girls, and children with special needs. Provide elementary school pupils life skills and computer abilities, focusing on girls and special needs kids.

Atma Nirbhar Bharat through Samagra Shiksha Scheme

It was announced that a National Foundational Literacy and Numeracy Mission would be launched as part of the 'Atma Nirbhar Bharat' campaign. The mission's goal is to ensure that by 2026-27, every child in the country will have attained a minimum level of literacy and numeracy equivalent to that achieved in Grade 3 across the country. This goal will be met by ensuring that by 2026-27, every child in the country will have attained a minimum level as a component of Samagra Shiksha, the "National Initiative for Proficiency in Reading with Understanding and Numeracy (NIPUN Bharat)" was launched on July 5, 2021. This event took place in Bharat.

Achievements

The initiative involves 11.6 lakh government-aided schools, 15.6 crore pupils, and 57 lakh instructors (from pre-primary to senior secondary level). From 2018-19 to 2021-22 (31.12.2021), the Scheme achieved the following---

73 new residential schools/hostels, 52668 schools reinforced (including additional classrooms), 15976 schools covered with ICT & Digital programs, 5900 schools offer vocational education, 788 KGBVs have been upgraded from class VIII to class X, 980 have been upgraded to class XII, and 13787 separate female restrooms have been built.

Conclusion

It will be possible for the State council of educational research and training to consolidate all of the in-service training programs under a single overarching plan, which will make such programs more dynamic and need-focused. A greater number of people would have access to education of a high standard, and the technical gains provided by the program would be available to all of the States that make up the Society. In an effort to produce educated, employable, and competitive human resources for a variety of industries and markets all over the world, the system makes an effort to combine general academic education with vocational education. The initiative includes participation from public universities. The program is currently applicable to 55 job roles across 19 industries, including agriculture, apparel made ups and home furnishing, automotive, banking finance and insurance services, beauty and wellness, construction, electronics and hardware, healthcare, information technology/IT enabled services, media and entertainment, multi-skilling, physical education and sports, plumber, power retail, security, telecommunications, tourism and hospitality, and transportation logistics and warehousing.

Educational Implications

The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan was responsible for the establishment of elementary schools and the acquisition of essential infrastructure. This made it possible for teachers to effectively educate students. The process of teaching and learning has been significantly enhanced in schools as a result of free textbooks, reference books, additional books, and other learning resources. The initiative provided the necessary resources for schools, allowing students to be taught and educated. Vocational education prepares graduates for jobs. It gives hands-on training so students may start their careers straight away.

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